

IMPROVING LABOR PRODUCTIVITY IN ROAD TRANSPORT

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Annotation: This article discusses the issues of improving labor productivity in road transport. It analyzes technical, organizational, social, and innovative factors that affect efficiency. Particular attention is paid to the implementation of modern technologies, improvement of logistics processes, and professional development of employees. The paper concludes with practical recommendations for the rational use of resources and improvement of working conditions.

Keywords: road transport, labor productivity, efficiency, logistics, technology, organizational measures, transport system.

Introduction

The transport system is an important link in the economy, and its effective operation has a positive impact on all sectors of production. Since road transport occupies a leading position in freight and passenger transportation, the issue of increasing labor productivity in it is one of the most urgent areas. Labor productivity not only increases the income of transport enterprises, but also ensures the effective functioning of the entire economy.

Today, the use of digital technologies, automated control systems, and environmentally friendly vehicles in the transport sector allows for a sharp increase in labor productivity. Therefore, this article will cover the theoretical foundations and practical ways to increase labor productivity in road transport. Mehnat unumdorligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar

The following factors significantly affect labor productivity in road transport:

1. Technical factors. The technical condition of vehicles, their fuel consumption, environmental performance, and repair system directly affect productivity.

2. Organizational factors. Rational distribution of labor, rational organization of working hours, optimization of routes, and reduction of empty trips increase productivity.

3. Social factors. The qualifications of employees, their working conditions, incentive system, and professional development opportunities have a significant impact on production productivity.

4. Innovative factors. GPS monitoring, telematics systems, electronic document management, automated control programs, artificial intelligence, and digital logistics solutions serve to effectively manage transport processes.

Ways to increase labor productivity

1. Modernization of the transport fleet. Phased renewal of old and uneconomical vehicles.

2. Improvement of technical maintenance. Preventing breakdowns through scheduled technical inspections.

3. Developing the logistics system. Optimizing routes and controlling cargo through electronic management programs.

4. Improving personnel skills. Organizing ongoing training programs for drivers, mechanics, and logisticians.

5. Introducing digital technologies. Saving time and money through automated accounting and monitoring systems.

6. Improving working conditions. Increasing motivation by ensuring the safety and comfort of workers.

Conclusion

Increasing labor productivity in road transport is one of the necessary conditions for the country's economic development. In this process, technical modernization, organizational measures, staff training and the widespread introduction of innovative technologies are of great importance. Also, through rational use of resources and improvement of working conditions, it is possible to improve the quality of transport services and reduce costs.

In order to increase labor productivity in road transport in the future, it is an urgent task to introduce the concept of a "digital transport system", increase the number of environmentally friendly vehicles and create integrated logistics centers.

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